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EXECUTIVE FUNCTION AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN EDUCATION

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Abstract

Executive functions are an umbrella term for the neurologically-based skills involving mental control and self-regulation. Some of the skills of executive function include components of reasoning, attention, planning, inhibition, set-shifting, working memory and the ability to regulate interference (Pennington, Ozonoff, 1996). The development of executive function emerges in late infancy, goes through marked changes during the ages of 2 through 6, and does not peak until around age 25. A person's executive functions are shaped by physical changes and also by ongoing experiences which means that as a person matures they develop better executive functioning skills with practice.

Many children have difficulties with one or more executive functions and are often undiagnosed. But their problems are usually identifiable through school. Children with executive functioning difficulties often manifest as Alternative Learners, or students who struggle in traditional classrooms. Intervention is crucial to students with various aspects of executive deficiencies to increase their functioning academically, socially, and to provide them with skills to develop independence and autonomy across the lifespan. This paper attempts to explain the significance of executive functioning in education.

Key words: Education, Executive functions, Children, traditional class room.

INTRODUCTION

Executive functions are a set of processes that all have to do with managing oneself and one's resources in order to achieve a goal. It is an umbrella term for the neurologically-based skills involving mental control and self-regulation. Some of the skills include components of reasoning, attention, planning, inhibition, set-shifting, working memory and the ability to regulate interference (Pennington, Ozonoff, 1996). These skills are necessary for adequate performance in all areas of daily life. They allow us to organise our behaviour, help us to plan activities, sustain attention, complete tasks and achieve long term goals. Executive function also enables the person to recognize the significance of unexpected situations and to make alternative plans quickly when unusual events arise and interfere with normal routines.

ASSESSMENT OF EXECUTIVE FUNCTION

Assessment of executive functioning is very challenging task as there are many factors that can contribute to impairment in executive functioning. There's no single test to identify executive function problems as it involves a set of interrelated skills. However psychologists, teachers, speech-language pathologists, and therapists rely on

different tests to assess specific skills of executive function assessment involves gathering data from several sources and synthesizing the information to look for trends and patterns across time and setting.

The traditional method of evaluating executive functioning has evolved administering neuropsychological or psychological tests. There has been a long history of using structured behavioural rating scales to assess psychological and neurological constructs (Reynolds & Kamphaus, 1992).

DEVELOPMENT OF EXECUTIVE FUNCTION

Executive functions develop over time, and as one progresses in age, changes are occurring and capacities are becoming more fully developed. A person's executive functions are shaped by physical changes and also by ongoing experiences which means that as a person matures they develop better executive functioning skills with practice. However the development of executive function emerges in late infancy, goes through marked changes during the ages of 2 through 6, and does not peak until around age 25. Several researchers have attempted to analyze the stages of development of executive function. For much of the twentieth century research on executive function centered almost exclusively on adults This was mainly because the prefrontal cortex was thought to become functionally mature only late in development; around adolescence (Luria, 1973).

However there is a growing body of research that suggests executive functions develop substantially during the school years (Romine & Reynolds, 2005) with seeds being planted early in the preschool years (Best, Miller, & Jones, 2009) that will become more fully developed in the later years. For example, cueing, inhibition, and working memory have been suggested to develop at younger ages, whereas shifting and planning are thought to develop in late childhood and adolescence (Jacques & Marcovitch, 2010).

Executive functioning skills take a long time to fully develop, therefore until the child acquires the skill (e.g., looking out for cars while crossing a street) parents should act as the child's executive functioning skills. At once the child develops the skill to maintain safety while crossing the street and it becomes internalized; the external cuing/direction from the parent are no longer needed.

SKILLS OF EXECUTIVE FUNCTION

There are several key skills involved in executive function. Some of them are

1. **Impulse control:** Ability to stop and think before acting.
2. **Emotional control:** Ability to manage her feelings by focusing on the end result or goal. Emotional control and impulse control are closely related.
3. **Flexibility:** Ability to roll with the punches and come up with new approaches when a plan fails.
4. **Working memory:** Ability to hold information in her mind and use it to complete a task.
5. **Self-monitoring:** Ability to keep track of and evaluate her performance on regular tasks.
6. **Planning and prioritizing:** Ability come up with the steps needed to reach a goal and to decide their order of importance.
7. **Task initiation:** Ability to get started on something.
8. **Organization:** Ability to keep track of information and things.

If a child has any or all of these issues, he/she may feel upset. But there are strategies to help the child learn to work around these weaknesses. Kids with mild to moderate weaknesses are able to compensate for them well enough to learn and complete everyday tasks.

IDENTIFYING EXECUTIVE FUNCTIONING ISSUES IN CHILDREN

Many children have difficulties with one or more executive functions. Executive functioning issues aren't considered a disability on their own. In fact, most people who struggle with executive functioning are never "diagnosed" with a problem but simply see it as an area of weakness in a key set of mental skills. And they often

appear in kids with learning and attention issues. In fact, some experts believe nearly all kids with ADHD have symptoms of executive functioning issues.

Executive functioning difficulties are often undiagnosed in many children, but their problems are usually identifiable through school. Children with executive functioning difficulties often manifest as Alternative Learners, or students who struggle in traditional classrooms. Identifying executive function issues among children is to see how the process of executive functioning works. Here is an example of how the process works, broken down into six steps:

1. Analyze a task. Figure out what needs to be done.
2. Plan how to handle the task.
3. Get organized. Break down the plan into a series of steps.
4. Figure out how much time is needed to carry out the plan, and set aside the time.
5. Make adjustments as needed
6. Finish the task in the time allotted.

If executive functioning is working well and the task is fairly simple, the brain may go through these steps in a matter of seconds. If the child has weak executive skills, though, performing even a simple task can be challenging.

ROLE OF EXECUTIVE FUNCTIONS IN EDUCATION

Most educators would agree that a purpose of education is to assist learners in developing life skills which will translate to their lives outside of the school setting. These include goal setting, organizational skills, time management, and strategies to learn new things. They are precursors to learning, skills or ability sets that are important for students to learn any content area knowledge. These are often discussed in the context of executive functions.

Executive functions impacts a student's ability to socialize with their friends, converse with their teacher and other staff members, homework completion and simply getting to and from school. Researchers have found that when children exhibit executive function, they are able to learn more in the classroom, because they can focus on the teacher and their work. However the demand for executive functions is limited until the upper elementary grades and, most notably, the middle school years (Holmes, 1987). As children make the adjustment from learning specific academic skills (e.g., reading writing, calculating) to applying these skills for learning content areas (e.g., literary analysis, report writing, algebra) the demand increases dramatically. As children enter middle school, they must also contend with significantly less organizational support than they had in elementary school.

Children with deficits in executive function may have difficulties in inhibiting impulses and considering alternative responses which can also lead them to be rejected by peers. Therefore, intervention is crucial to students with various aspects of executive deficiencies to increase their functioning academically, socially, and to provide them with skills to develop independence and autonomy across the lifespan. Specific areas of intervention may address one or more of the commonly considered areas of executive functioning. Below are some simple practical strategies that can be used in a classroom for a student experiencing executive functioning difficulties.

Students with weak Executive Function skills need strong support and specific strategies to help them learn in an efficient manner, demonstrate what they know, and manage the daily demands of school. Therefore with the aid of the above strategies, teachers should aim to make the learning process for a child with executive functioning difficulties as visual and as concrete as possible.

S.NO	Skills of executive function	Difficulties	Intervention/Strategies
1.	Impulse control	Blurt out inappropriate things. Engages in risky behavior	Provide specific guidelines in form of Cognitive script to train how to behave in certain situations. Script can be in form of a visual cue. Prompting the individual regarding expected behaviors in a specific situation.
2.	Emotional control	Overreact and have trouble dealing with criticism and regrouping when something goes wrong	Teach ways to manage anger and impulse control by recognizing the emotion, taking deep breaths, and thinking calming thoughts, and finding ways to solve the problem.
3.	Flexibility	Gets frustrated if asked to think about something from a different angle	Provide opportunities for the student to change environments
4.	Working memory	Have trouble remembering things even if they have taken notes or repeated them several times.	Provide a reminder to help complete task viz. verbal reminder like saying a word/phrase or providing a note book/computer to do lists.
5.	Self-monitoring	Unlikely to check work for mistakes; is unaware of own behavior and its impact on others.	Have students self-question, build in self-reflection activities by having students record strategies they used like what was helpful? What would I do differently next time?
6.	Planning and prioritizing	May start assignments at the last minute; does not think ahead about possible problems.	Provide a visual timetable which illustrates what to do in a picture format. Templates for completing regular tasks/assignments can be provided to the pupil with headings
7.	Task initiation	Might freeze up without having idea where to begin	Help the student get started on writing assignments by talking through the first few sentences or so. Provide scaffold such as sentence starters and frames
8.	Organization	Often has a scattered or disorganized approach to solving a problem; is easily overwhelmed by large tasks or assignments.	Break down tasks into component parts and provide a checklist for each component, e.g., what materials are needed to complete each part.

CONCLUSION

Executive function plays a critical role in student academic performance. In fact, academic success is largely dependent on a student's ability to plan, organize, and prioritize information, regulate his/her attention, manipulate information in working memory, monitor his/her progress, and reflect on his/her work. Students who have dysfunctions in executive function will struggle in the classroom. Therefore teachers must model good use of executive functions and ways to handle the lapses in executive function that are part of normal life. A better understanding of student's deficits and ways to address their needs helps them to achieve better.

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